

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF ASSAY OF METOCLOPRAMIDE HYDROCHLORIDE API BY USING REVERSE PHASE HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

The developed High Performance liquid Chromatography (HPLC) method for the analysis of Development and Validation of assay of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API is Precise and feasible. The separation was carried out on the Hypersil C18 Column, (length- 250mm x Inner Diameter-4.6 mm), 5.0 μm ; using 28:72 of Ammonium acetate Buffer and Acetonitrile as Mobile Phase, with Flow rate 1.0 mL/min, Column temperature-40°C, Sample temperature- 15°C, Wavelength at 210nm, Injection volume is 10 μL , Run time-10 minutes, Diluent-1 is Ethanol and Diluent-2 is Water. Peak shape found satisfactory. System suitability parameter were meets the acceptance criteria and %Relative standard deviation was within the limit. The Correlation coefficient of Linearity for individual solvent, obtained from three replicate injection are not less than 0.998. And all the level of Recoveries are within the limit of 80% to 120%. The method was validated as per International Council for Harmonization (ICH) norms and

the method is also cost effective. The proposed method is useful for rapid analysis of

estimation of Assay in Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API.

KEYWORDS: High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API, UV Detector.

INTRODUCTION

PHARMACEUTICAL ANALYSIS

Analysis involves the qualitative and quantitative identification of the individual components of substances, samples, or mixtures. There are two different kinds of analysis. Qualitative analysis and Quantitative analysis. The identification of mixture of sample's constituents or analytes is done by qualitative analysis.^[1] Quantitative analysis involves calculating the quantity of each component or analyte in a mixture or sample.

CHROMATOGRAPHY

Chromatography is essentially a group of techniques for the separation of the compounds of mixture by their continuous distribution in two phases one which moving past the other.^[2]

Term	Definition
Chromatography	Method for separation
Chromatograph	Instrument for chromatography
Chromatogram	Data of chromatography

HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY^[3-9]

High-pressure liquid chromatography is also referred to as HPLC (high performance liquid chromatography). Any component present in a sample that can dissolve in liquid can be separated, identified, and quantified using HPLC.

Adsorption is the major principle behind liquid chromatography. Mobile phase is a liquid used with this chromatographic method. The sample is a liquid solution. A sample is injected into a column that is composed of a stationary phase of porous material and a mobile phase of liquid material. A pump's high pressure delivery of the mobile phase leads the sample to move throughout the column. Sample elements move in accordance with the affine they are to the stationary phase. The component which has greater attraction to the stationary phase moves more slowly.^[10] The component that moves more quickly has a lower attraction for the stationary phase. The parts are kept apart from one another. N-hexane, methylene chloride, chloroform, methyl-t-butyl ether, isopropanol (IPA), acetonitrile (ACN), methanol (MeOH), water and tetrahydrofuran (THF) are the most often used solvents for HPLC.

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT^[10-14]

Development of analytical methods is the process of selecting an accurate assay method to determine a formulation's composition. The process of developing an analytical method is used to demonstrate that an analytical method is appropriate for usage in a laboratory. Analytical methods must be prepared using the provided protocols and acceptance criteria in the ICH guidelines Q2 (R1) and applied in GMP and GLP environments.

METHOD OPTIMIZATION^[15]

The experimental conditions should be optimized to get desired separations and sensitivity after getting appropriate separations. This will be achieved through planned/systemic examination of parameters. During optimization one parameter is changed at a time and set of conditions are isolated rather than using a trial and error approach.

METHOD VALIDATION^[15-16]

Validation is derived from Latin from which means “strongness”. Validation is the strength or strongness of a procedure, process, and capability of an equipment to operate and is proved for its acceptability with confirmation and documented legally on the basis of scientific data.

METOCLOPRAMIDE HYDROCHLORIDE API

Molecular formula: C₁₄H₂₅Cl₂N₃O₃ Molecular weight: 299.80 g·mol⁻¹

IUPAC Name: 4-Amino-5-chloro-N-[2-(diethylamino)ethyl]-o-anisamide monohydrochloride monohydrate.

Description: White or off-white crystalline powder Indication:

- Drug indicated for the Medication primarily used as an antiemetic to prevent and treat nausea and vomiting and as a prokinetic agent to speed up stomach emptying. Its indication varies depending on the patient's age and the specific condition.

MODE OF ACTION

Metoclopramide Hydrochloride works primarily as a dopamine (D2) receptor antagonist and a serotonin (5-HT₄) receptor agonist, enhancing gastrointestinal motility and preventing nausea and vomiting through central and peripheral actions.

Central Mechanism — Anti-Emetic Effect

Metoclopramide exerts antiemetic effects by antagonizing dopamine D2 receptors in the chemoreceptor trigger zone (CTZ) of the brainstem. The CTZ is a central area that detects emetogenic stimuli, such as toxins, drugs, or metabolic triggers, and activates the vomiting reflex. By blocking these D2 receptors, Metoclopramide prevents nausea and vomiting, making it particularly effective in chemotherapy-induced, postoperative, or pregnancy-related nausea.

Summary of Actions

- Anti-nausea and anti-vomiting: Central D2 receptor blockade in the CTZ.
- Gastrokinetic: D2 antagonism plus 5-HT₄ agonism enhances gastric emptying and intestinal motility.
- GERD control: Increased LES tone reduces gastroesophageal reflux.
- Other serotonergic effects: Minor involvement at 5-HT₃ receptors at high doses to reduce chemotherapy-induced vomiting.

TOXICITY

Metoclopramide hydrochloride can cause neurological, cardiovascular, endocrine, and gastrointestinal toxicities, with serious complications including extrapyramidal symptoms, tardive dyskinesia, and, rarely, neuroleptic malignant syndrome. Acute overdose usually produces CNS depression and dystonic reactions.

METHODOLOGY

Instrument : HPLC equipped with UV-Vis Detector

Mode : Isocratic

Column : Hypersil C18(250mm × 4.6 mm),5µmColumn

Temperature : 40°C

Sampler temperature : 15°C

Flow rate : 1.0mL/minute

Wavelength : 210 nm

Injection Volume : 10 μ L

Run time : 10 minutes

Preparation of Solutions Diluent (Internal Standard)

Preparation of Diluents: Diluent-1: Ethanol

Preparation of standard solution

Weigh and transfer accurately about 80 mg of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride working standard into a 25mL volumetric flask, add about 5mL of ethanol and sonicate to dissolve. Make up the volume with water and mix well. Further dilute 5mL of above solution to 20mL volumetric flask, make up volume with water mix well (about 800.0 μ g/mL of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride).

Preparation of sample Solution

Weigh and transfer accurately about 80 mg of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride sample into a 25mL volumetric flask, add about 5mL of ethanol and sonicate to dissolve. Make up the volume with water and mix well. Further dilute 5mL of above solution to 20mL volumetric flask, make up volume with water mix well (about 800.0 μ g/mL of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride).

Preparation of Linearity Solutions

Preparation of linearity stock standard solution

Weigh and transfer accurately 200.0mg of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride reference/working standard into a 50mL volumetric flask. Add about 10mL of ethanol and sonicate to dissolve the contents completely with intermediate shaking and make up to volume with water, mix well. (Nominal concentration: 4000 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride).

- a) **Preparation of linearity solution-1 (50%):** Pipette out 2mL of above stock solution into 20mL volumetric flask make up to the volume with the water. (about 400.0 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API)
- b) **Preparation of linearity solution-2 (75%):** Pipette out 3mL of above stock solution into 20mL volumetric flask make up to the volume with the water. (about 600 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API)
- c) **Preparation of linearity solution-3 (100%):** Pipette out 4mL of above stock solution into 20mL volumetric flask make up to the volume with the water. (about 800 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API)

- d) **Preparation of linearity solution-4 (125%):** Pipette out 5mL of above stock solution into 20mL volumetric flask make up to the volume with the water. (about 1000 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API)
- e) **Preparation of linearity solution-5 (150%):** Pipette out 6mL of above stock solution into 20mL volumetric flask make up to the volume with the water. (about 1200 μ g/mL for

Preparation of Accuracy Solutions

Preparation of Accuracy stock solution

Weigh and transfer accurately 200.0mg of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride Sample into a 50mL volumetric flask. Add about 10mL of ethanol and sonicate to dissolve the contents completely with intermediate shaking and make up to volume with water, mix well. (Nominal concentration: 4000 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride).

Preparation of Accuracy solution-1 (50%)

Pipette out 2mL of above stock solution into 20mL volumetric flask make up to the volume with the water. (About 400.0 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride).

Preparation of Accuracy solution-2 (100%)

Pipette out 4mL of above stock solution into 20mL volumetric flask make up to the volume with the water. (about 800 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride).

Preparation of Accuracy solution-1 (150%)

Pipette out 6mL of above stock solution into 20mL volumetric flask make up to the volume with the water. (about 1200 μ g/mL for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride).

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT

Trial -1

Observation

In trial-1 the peak is looks like **splitter of three peaks**, and it's not a single sharp peak. Hence, method needs to be developed further.

Trial -2:

Observation

In trial-2 the peak is looks like **hump in tailing**, and it's not a single sharp peak. Hence, method needs to be developed further.

Trial -3:

Observation

In trial-3 the peak is looks like **hump in fronting**, and it's not a single sharp peak. Hence, method needs to be developed further.

ANALYTICAL METHOD VALIDATION

Specificity

The specificity of method was monitored by analyzing the Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API

and standard solution. No peak was detected in close to the retention time of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API, which proved to be high degree of specificity of the method.

A

B

C

Chromatogram A – Blank, B – Standard, C – Sample.

Result from optimized method.

Name	Observations
Blank	No interference was observed
Time of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API	
Standard solution	4.86
Sample solution	4.85

System suitability.

SYSTEM SUITABILITY			
System suitability test parameter	Observation	Limit	Conclusion
% RSD for replicate Std	0.2	NMT 2.0%	Pass
Theoretical plate count	10454	NLT 2000	Pass
Tailing factor	1.2	NMT 2.0	Pass
Similarity factor	1.00	0.98-1.02	Pass
% RSD of BKT Std	0.2	NMT 2.0%	Pass

PRECISION SYSTEM PRECISION

The precision of instrument was checked by checking the area consistency of same solution with multiple injections.

Standard Injection	Area for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API
1	193911
2	193795
3	193095
4	193229
5	193029
6	193326
Average	193398
Standard deviation	369.457
% RSD	0.2

METHOD PRECISION

The precision of the method was checked by preparing six independent test solutions from sample and injected into HPLC system. The results are tabulated below.

Results for Method precision

Sample No.	% Assay
1	103.1
2	102.7
3	103.0
4	102.9
5	102.9
6	102.9
Average	102.9
STDEV	0.133
% RSD	0.1

LINEARITY AND RANGE

Linearity of the analytical method for the estimation of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API by

injecting the various concentrations of standard preparation in the range of 50% to 150% of sample concentration into the chromatograph by covering minimum of 5 different concentrations.

Results from linearity.

Correlation Coefficient r	0.9999
Regression Coefficient r ²	0.9998
% Y-intercept	2932.1492
Intercept	1.29
Residual sum square	284.4200
Slope	1439.7915

The results obtained from Linearity experiment was met as per above acceptance. This result shows that method is acceptable with respect to linearity.

RANGE

Range of the analytical method for the estimation of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API by injecting three concentrations of standard preparation in the range are 50%, 100% and 150% of sample concentration into the chromatograph. It could be referred from Accuracy Sample.

Results of range.

Injection	50% Level	100% Level	150% Level
1	115969	224290	335912
2	115876	224149	342100
3	115805	224629	333142
% RSD	0.1	0.1	1.4

The results obtained from Linearity experiment was met as per above acceptance. This result shows that method is acceptable with respect to linearity.

ACCURACY

Level-I : 50% of sample concentration

Level-II : 100% of sample concentration

Level-III : 150% of sample concentration.

Result of method Accuracy.

Level	Mean area	Amount found (mg)	Amount added (mg)	%Recovery	Avg	% RSD
50% - 1	114969	445.0826	433.6833	102.6	102.6	0.1
50% - 2	114876	444.7225	433.6833	102.5		
50% - 3	114805	444.4477	433.6833	102.5		
100% - 1	224290	868.2999	866.8337	100.2	100.2	0.1
100% - 2	224149	867.7540	866.8337	100.1		
100% - 3	224629	869.6122	866.8337	100.3		
150% - 1	335912	1300.4251	1298.5334	100.1	100.5	1.4
150% - 2	342100	1324.3808	1298.5334	102.0		
150% - 3	333142	1289.7015	1298.5334	99.3		

The results obtained from accuracy experiment was met as per above acceptance criteria set in the analytical method validation protocol. This result shows that the method is acceptable with respect to accuracy.

STABILITY OF THE ANALYTICAL SOLUTIONS

Analytical solution stability

The stability of sample solutions and standard solution was established by injecting the solution after 24 hours' storage at room temperature against a freshly prepared standard.

Result of sample solution stability.

Sample Solution	Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API At 15°C	
	%Assay	% Absolute Difference
Initial	103.2	NA
12Hr	103.1	0.10
17Hr	103.2	0.00
22Hr	102.6	0.58
36Hr	102.3	0.87

Result of standard solution stability

Standard Solution	Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API At 15°C	
	Area(mAU)	% RSD
Initial	193911	NA
12Hr	192752	0.24
17Hr	192714	0.24
22Hr	192800	0.23
24Hr	192819	0.23
29Hr	192212	0.32
36Hr	191859	0.38

The stability of the standard solution was proved upto 36 hours and 36 hours for sample solution of Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API at 15°C.

ROBUSTNESS

The robustness of the analytical method was checked by applying deliberate change of Column temperature, Flow rate in the specified instrument method and Organic Composition of mobile phase.

Results for Flow Rate Change in Robustness.

Sample preparation	% Assay	% Absolute Difference	Conclusion
Actual Flow (1.0ml/min)	102.7	NA	NA
Low Flow (0.9 ml/min)	102.7	0.0	Complies
High Flow (1.1 ml/min)	102.6	0.1	Complies

Results for Column Temperature Change in Robustness.

Sample preparation	% Assay	% Absolute Difference	Conclusion
Actual Temperature 45°C	102.7	NA	NA
Low Temperature 40°C	102.7	0.0	Complies
High Temperature 50°C	103.1	0.4	Complies

Results for Organic Composition change in Robustness.

Sample preparation	% Assay	% Absolute Difference	Conclusion
Actual Organic	102.7	NA	NA
Low Organic	102.9	0.2	Complies
High Organic	103.2	0.5	Complies

CONCLUSION

In the present research, a fast, simple, accurate, precise, and linear stability-indicating HPLC method has been developed and validated for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API, and hence it can be employed for routine analysis. The analytical method conditions and the mobile phase solvents provided good resolution for Metoclopramide Hydrochloride API. In addition,

the main features of the developed method are short run time and retention time around 4.7 min. The method was validated in accordance with ICH guidelines. The method is robust enough to reproduce accurate and precise results under different chromatographic conditions.

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